

GRANULAR MATERIALS AND THEIR POTENTIAL VISUALIZATION FEATURE

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Abstract. Granular materials, which are the second most manipulated system in industry after water, can be used also as visualization media. This type of materials consists of a lot of solid particles with or without interstitial fluid. With existence of gravitation the particles are normally condensed to the bottom of the container or suspended by its ambient atmosphere, but with external stimulation in the form of vibration, fluid flow, or electromagnetic field, particles arrangement can be changed. By choosing certain colors for particles and its background, they can act as a visualization system, where the particles are the pixels. Properties of the particles and the environment must be chosen carefully and also tuned to get the desired results. Gas pressure, magnetic field, electric field, fluid flow are examples of physical properties that can be visualized using these materials.

Keywords: granular materials; dynamics system; pattern; visualization feature; transdisciplinary approach.

1 Introduction

Materials, that can be found everywhere and are the second-most manipulated (water is the first) in industry, are granular materials, whose applications ranging from micrometer size in pharmaceutical, e.g. medicine powder, until decimeter size in geological, e.g. rock avalanches and debris flows [1], or beyond kilometer size in astronomy, e.g. asteroids state other than rigid one [2]. The earliest use of granular materials as visualization materials could be addressed to magnetic fringe fields around permanent magnet and current carrying wire as revealed by Oersted, Davy, Ampere with the aid of iron powder [3]. And later, as its counter part, electric fringe fields can also be visualised using semolina seeds poured on surface of castor oil [4]. In dynamic system falling white sand on the black background is used to draw the projection of a spherical pendulum trajectory [5]. In the field of acoustics visualization of sound around a diffuser is performed with the help of fine cork powder [6]. By varying amplitude and frequency of oscillation vibrated granular layers will have certain phase, where each differs in the observed pattern, e.g. zig-zag instability, unstable hexagons, phase-disordered patterns, and “two-phase” squares [7]. Previous examples are the use of granular materials with natural interactions, e.g. magnetic field, electric field, gravitation field, collision, buoyancy, and next we can also use artificial interactions to manipulate granular particles. With the help of computers and controllers these days beads, when they are considered as granular particles, can be manipulated using string to form a one-layer three-dimensional surface, which now known as part of kinetic sculptures [8-11]. Sand can also barely be used as pixels in monochrome [12] or colored two-dimensional horizontal [13], or pseudo two-dimensional vertical static painting [14].

2 Grains as pixels

Concept of pixel is normally used in digital display or printing results, which represent the smallest element or simply a point in a picture that can have certain color different than its background or surrounding pixels. Grains as granular materials, that are also small and sometimes is considered as point, can also be used as pixels in visualizing physical properties or simply artwork.

2.1 Two-dimensional painting

The term sand painting is actually not so right since we do not use paint anymore in performing the painting process, but sand. Figure 1 shows monochrome two-dimensional horizontal sand painting. Color of the sand that is different than its background acts as monochrome dark brown pixel on the white background.

Figure 1. Sand painting for Titanic [12].

We can also give color the sand and used in to colorize different region in the picture as shown in figure 2 for Sand Mandala [13]. This is an example of color two-dimensional horizontal sand painting. Normally it has only one to several layers of sand but with the same color.

Figure 2. Sand Mandala [13].

Other than two-dimensional horizontal painting, a pseudo two-dimensional vertical painting has also been practicing as shown in figure 3, which is an introduction to sand tapestry by David Alcala [14]. It uses gravity and friction between sand grains to make the sand static.

Figure 3. Sand tapestry [14].

In this type of sand painting gradation and mixture of color can be performed using a small stick as a paint brush. Different than the previous type of sand painting, this one requires order of painting must be started from bottom to top of the painting.

2.2 Three-dimensional figures

There are two three-dimensional figures constructed from sand presented in this part. The first is a sand castle in figure 4 and the last is a universal robotic gripper in figure 5. These two different types of three-dimensional figures use different physical laws to maintain their static conditions. A sand castle requires help from gravitation, friction, and water-bridge binding, while a universal robotic gripper requires friction and negative pressure to construct granular jamming.

Figure 4. Process of building a sand castle [15].

Figure 5. Universal robotic gripper while gripping various forms [16].

It is interesting to further explore the universal robotic gripper for not-so-useful figures but only artworks. In this three-dimensional object we cannot put the pixels, i.e. the sand grains, in arbitrary positions but must be constructed from bottom to top, where bottom is position with lower potential energy and top is position with higher potential energy.

2.3 Electromagnetic fringe fields

In an electromagnetic field, magnetic and electric fields have different ways of interaction with matter. A magnetic field can attract inducible materials and attract-repel magnetized materials, while an electric field can attract or repel material with different or same type of charge. Visualization of magnetic and electric fringe fields uses the way how these two fields interact with matter, i.e. granular materials, as shown in figures 6 and 7.

Figure 6. Visualization of magnetic fringe fields using iron powder [3]

Figure 7. Visualization of electric fringe fields using semolina seeds poured on surface of castor oil [4].

2.4 Vibration mode of a plate

When a horizontal plate vibrated there are some stationary waves produced that can be visualized using granular materials and the patterns are very dependent on vibration frequency as given in figure 8.

Figure 7. Visualization of plate vibration using sand grains as the pixels with various vibration frequency: 345, 1033, 1820, 2041, 3240, 3835, 3975, 4129, 4671, 4840, 5201, and 5284 Hz [17].

2.5 Wire-suspended-floating one-layer beads

Beads in many forms can also be suspended in air with vertical wire system to produce a “floating-effect”. And by scrolling the wire vertically, height of the beads can be manipulated, that produces a three-dimensional one-layer surface. Several systems have been installed publicly as shown in figure 8.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 8. Kinetic sculpture installed in various places: (a) BMW Museum, (b) 2010 World Expo, (c) Build UP LLC, and (c) Kinetic rain in Singapore Changi airport terminal 1.

In this system grains do not interact to each and can only move in vertical direction. A configuration of beads will produce a one-layer three-dimensional object floating in the air. Formerly beads can only have their own static color as in figure 8 (a) and 8 (b), but later they can be LED lamps with various possible color as in figure 8 (c), or simply change the form of the beads like water droplets as in figure 9 (d).

3 Discussion

Beads, grains, sand, and powder, that are all in the category of granular materials, a type of materials that has been proposed as an additional state of matter [18], have a unique potential to be used in visualizing something such as electromagnetic fringe field, vibration state of a plate, or trajectory projection of a swinging pendulum. They can also be used in generating painting and three-dimensional objects. Friction between grains and gravitation (or pressure) play important role in make the grains static, which make colored grains functioning as pixels. There is a phenomenon of granular materials that supports segregation, i.e. Brazil-nut effect [19], which sets position of intruder in the surrounding bed particles environment due to vertical vibration as shown in figure 9.

Figure 9. Brazil-nut effect (image by Gszrdzł, CC BY-SA 3.0.) [19].

The question is how we can utilize the BNE (Brazil-nut effect) to control our pixel (intruder) to go up (or down as in reverse Brazil-nut effect or RBNE) as free as we desire? Air-driven liquefaction could be used for the reverse process that allow higher density objects to sink and lower ones to float as shown in figure 10.

Figure 9. Sand air-driven liquefaction [20].

What if we can combine these two mechanisms into a single system and produce a controlled pixel to go up and down as planned. Perhaps it could be an opportunity in constructing another granular materials-based display system.

4 Summary

Several systems including physical and electronical ones, that use granular materials as smallest display elements (or simply pixels) have been discussed and possibility to construct another type is also proposed by utilize the phenomena Brazil-nut effect and air-driven liquefaction.

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